

How Corporates Can Have A Good Advertising? (A Review Of Ethics & Crs In Advertising)

Author's Details:

Abbas Dadras¹, Seyed Naser Zahiri², Ali Memari³ and Zeinab Shahi⁴

¹ Assistance Professor, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

² Master of Business Management Student, Majoring in E-commerce, Graduate School, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

³ Master of Business Management Student, Majoring in E-commerce, Graduate School, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

⁴ Master of Business Management Student, Majoring in E-commerce, Graduate School, Collage of Humanities, Department of Business, Islamic Azad University, Bandar Abbas Branch, Hormozgan, Iran

*Corresponding author: Email: Abbas_dadras@yahoo.com

Abstract:

Prior to establishment of the CPPO (Consumers and Producers Protection Organization) in Iran, consumers had no protection against the claims of advertisers. Advertising in its simplest form means "public announcement". Just as the media of social communication themselves have enormous influence everywhere, so advertising, using media as its vehicle, is a pervasive, powerful force shaping attitudes and behavior in today's world.

Nowadays, ads are more exaggerated and a lot of puffing is used. It seems like the advertisers lack knowledge of ethical norms and principles. They just don't understand and are unable to decide what is correct and what is wrong. The main area of interest for advertisers is to increase their sales, gain more and more customers, and increase the demand for the product by presenting a well decorated, puffed and colorful ad. They claim that their product is the best, having unique qualities than the competitors, more cost effective, and more beneficial. But most of these ads are found to be false, misleading customers and unethical.

In other hand, over the past two decades there has been increased interest in corporate responsibility (CSR) and its relation to advertising. Although advertising has played a key role in bringing corporate social responsibility (CSR) to the public agenda on behalf of agency clients, little effort has been made to define what social responsibility means in advertising.

Our reason for addressing these matters is simple. In today's society, advertising has a profound impact on how people understand life, the world and themselves, especially in regard to their values and their ways of choosing and behaving. For these reasons, advertisers need to be more aware of corporates social responsibility, in addition to observing ethical issues and norms.

Keywords: Corporate Social Responsibility, Ethics, Advertising, Norms

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern day society, advertisements have a huge influence everywhere, especially those through the media. Advertising through the media is pervasive and powerful in shaping attitudes and behaviors in the contemporary world. Today, there is increasing literature focusing on ethical and moral issues that the advertisement can and does actually raise. Advertising encourages economic growth through information being made available about competing goods and services. However, advertising can be deceptive, encourage unlimited consumption, create confusion for the consumer, and intensify destructive desires such as lust and greed. Advertising encourages consumption by showing improvement in features and quality of products and services. Advertising is only one aspect that goes into shaping consumer choices, and the role advertising plays in either initiating or reinforcing consumer trends is dubious.

Advertisement by definition refers to structured, non-personal communication or information about products, services or a firm that is in most cases paid for. It is usually persuasive and about products by identified

sponsors through the various channels of the media. Therefore, it can be argue that advertising is multidimensional and is definitely a form of publicity.

Any form of mass communication has a social responsibility attached with it and thus advertisement is no exception. However, one question in this context that needs to be cleared is whether advertisements fulfill the 'so called responsibility' or not. Advertisements are meant for the masses and people relate themselves with this medium. Thus, for understanding its responsibilities towards the public, its positive and the negative aspects needs to understood. As a general rule, it refers to the obligation of the business to take deliberate actions that protect and improve the general good of the society as a whole. Ethics, on the other hand, means doing something right in the society's view. What is ethical is that which receives a common consent of the society. The focus of business in the 21st century should not be to earn profit alone, but to serve society in the most ethical and socially responsible way possible.

In this paper we address the topic of concern in terms of effect on the entire advertising industry. That is, the paper examines how the ethical and social responsibility practice of companies affects the advertising industry today. In addition, the paper attempts to explore various ways in which business managers use their practices in their advertising campaigns to achieve business goals. In addition, looking at how ethical and social responsibility practices affect consumer behavior, the paper further explores the implementation of such practices in specific organizations.

1.1. Benefits and Harms of Advertising

Advertising is a two-way tool. There is nothing intrinsically good or intrinsically evil about advertising. It is a tool, an instrument: it can be used well, and it can be used badly. For this reason, we review the benefits and harms of advertising in this part.

a) Benefits of Advertising

A.1. Economic Benefits of Advertising

Advertising can play a significant role in the process by which an economic system guided by moral norms and responsive to common good contributes to human development. It is a necessary part of the functioning of the modern market economies, which today either exist or are emerging in many parts of the world and which - provided they comply with moral standards based on the integral human development and common good - in the present seem to be "The most effective tool for utilizing resources and effectively responding to needs" of a socio-economic type.

In such a system, advertising can be a useful tool for maintaining a fair and ethically responsible competition that contributes to economic growth in the service of authentic human development.

Advertising does this, among other ways, by informing people about the availability of rationally desirable new products and services and improvements in existing ones, helping them to make informed, prudent consumer decisions, contributing to efficiency and lowering prices and stimulating economic progress through the expansion of business and trade. All of this can contribute to the creation of new jobs, higher incomes and a more decent and humane way of life for all.

A.2. Benefits of Political Advertising

Political advertising can make a contribution to democracy analogous to its contribution to economic wellbeing in a market system guided by moral norms. As free and responsible media in a democratic system help to counteract tendencies toward the monopolization of power on the part of oligarchies and special interests, so political advertising can make its contribution by

informing people about the ideas and policy proposals of parties and candidates, including new candidates not previously known to the public.

A.3 Cultural Benefits of Advertising

Because of the impact advertising has on media that depend on it for revenue, advertisers have an opportunity to exert a positive influence on decisions about media content. This they do by supporting material of excellent intellectual, aesthetic and moral quality presented with the public interest in view, and particularly by encouraging and making possible media presentations which are oriented to minorities whose needs might otherwise go unserved.

Moreover, advertising can itself contribute to the betterment of society by uplifting and inspiring people and motivating them to act in ways that benefit themselves and others. Advertising can brighten lives simply by being witty, tasteful and entertaining. Some advertisements are instances of popular art, with a vivacity and elan all their own.

A.4. Moral and Religious Benefits of Advertising

In many cases, too, benevolent social institutions, including those of a religious nature, use advertising to communicate their messages — messages of faith, of patriotism, of tolerance, compassion and neighborly service, of charity toward the needy, messages concerning health and education, constructive and helpful messages that educate and motivate people in a variety of beneficial ways.

b) Harms of Advertising

B.1. Economic Harms of Advertising

Advertising can betray its role as a source of information by misrepresentation and by withholding relevant facts. Sometimes, too, the information function of media can be subverted by advertisers' pressure upon publications or programs not to treat of questions that might prove embarrassing or inconvenient.

More often, though, advertising is used not simply to inform but to persuade and motivate to convince people to act in certain ways: buy certain products or services, patronize certain institutions, and the like. This is where particular abuses can occur.

The practice of "brand"-related advertising can raise serious problems. Often there are only negligible differences among similar products of different brands, and advertising may attempt to move people to act on the basis of irrational motives ("brand loyalty," status, fashion, "sex appeal," etc.) instead of presenting differences in product quality and price as bases for rational choice.

Advertising also can be, and often is, a tool of the "phenomenon of consumerism. Sometimes advertisers

speak of it as part of their task to "create" needs for products and services that is, to cause people to feel and act upon cravings for items and services they do not need.

" This is a serious abuse, an affront to human dignity and the common good when it occurs in affluent societies. But the abuse is still more grave when consumerist attitudes and values are transmitted by communications media and advertising to developing countries, where they exacerbate socio-economic problems and harm the poor. "It is true that a judicious use of advertising can stimulate developing countries to improve their standard of living. But serious harm can be done them if advertising and commercial pressure become so irresponsible that communities seeking to rise from poverty to a reasonable standard of living are persuaded to seek this progress by satisfying wants that have been artificially created. The result of this is that they waste their resources and neglect their real needs, and genuine development falls behind."

Similarly, the task of countries attempting to develop types of market economies that serve human needs and interests after decades under centralized, state-controlled systems is made more difficult by advertising that promotes consumerist attitudes and values offensive to human dignity and the common good. The problem is particularly acute when, as often happens, the dignity and welfare of society's poorer and weaker members are at stake.

B.2. Harms of Political Advertising

Political advertising can support and assist the working of the democratic process, but it also can obstruct it. This happens when, for example, the costs of advertising limit political competition to wealthy candidates or groups, or require that office-seekers compromise their integrity and independence by over-dependence on special interests for funds.

Such obstruction of the democratic process also happens when, instead of being a vehicle for honest expositions of candidates' views and records, political advertising seeks to distort the views and records of opponents and unjustly attacks their reputations. It happens when advertising appeals more to people's emotions and base instincts to selfishness, bias and hostility toward others, to racial and ethnic prejudice and the like rather than to a reasoned sense of justice and the good of all.

B.3. Cultural Harms of Advertising

Advertising also can have a corrupting influence upon culture and cultural values. We have spoken of the economic harm that can be done to developing nations by advertising that fosters consumerism and destructive patterns of consumption. Consider also the cultural injury done to these nations and their peoples by advertising

whose content and methods, reflecting those prevalent in the first world, are at war with sound traditional values in indigenous cultures. Today this kind of "domination and manipulation" via media rightly is "a concern of developing nations in relation to developed ones," as well as a "concern of minorities within particular nations."

The indirect but powerful influence exerted by advertising upon the media of social communications that depend on revenues from this source points to another sort of cultural concern. In the competition to attract ever larger audiences and deliver them to advertisers, communicators can find themselves tempted in fact pressured, subtly or not so subtly to set aside high artistic and moral standards and lapse into superficiality, tawdriness and moral squalor.

Communicators also can find themselves tempted to ignore the educational and social needs of certain segments of the audience the very young, the very old, the poor who do not match the demographic patterns (age, education, income, habits of buying and consuming, etc.) of the kinds of audiences advertisers want to reach. In this way the tone and indeed the level of moral responsibility of the communications media in general are lowered.

All too often, advertising contributes to the invidious stereotyping of particular groups that places them at a disadvantage in relation to others. This often is true of the way advertising treats women or kids.

B.4. Moral and Religious Harms of Advertising

Advertising can be tasteful and in conformity with high moral standards, and occasionally even morally uplifting, but it also can be vulgar and morally degrading. Frequently it deliberately appeals to such motives as envy, status seeking and lust. Today, too, some advertisers consciously seek to shock and titillate by exploiting content of a morbid, perverse, pornographic nature.

Also, commercial advertisers sometimes include religious themes or use religious images or personages to sell products. It is possible to do this in tasteful, acceptable ways, but the practice is obnoxious and offensive when it involves exploiting religion or treating it flippantly.

Furthermore, advertising sometimes is used to promote products and inculcate attitudes and forms of behavior contrary to moral norms. That is the case, for instance, with the advertising of contraceptives, abortifacients and products harmful to health, and with government-sponsored advertising campaigns for artificial birth control, so-called "safe sex", and similar practices.

1.2. What is CSR?

While the term Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) was coined in the 1950s, the concept has its roots in

social contract theory dating back to 1600s. CSR has been described as an organisation's social obligation: to pursue policies, make decisions or take actions that are in line with societal objectives and values. More recently, CSR has been considered in relation to the groups or stakeholders that are directly or indirectly affected by the activities of the organisation, such as employees, customers, shareholders, suppliers and the local community. The benefits of CSR for an organisation can include increased customer loyalty, employee commitment, supplier support and improved corporate reputation. CSR can be seen as part of a greater change in corporate philosophy and practice over the past two decades: the business ethics movement.

Fundamentally, socially responsible behavior internalizes all external consequences of an action, both its costs and benefits. But there is a problem with this definition. What should a company value in its pursuit of social responsibility? Should it attempt to minimize the negative impacts of its business activity, or maximize its positive impacts, or find some optimal combination of positive and negative impacts? And how much do various stakeholders' preferences matter? Do the opinions of environmentalists count more than those of labor activists? Or shareholders? Or consumers?

Those questions can become so overwhelming and convoluted that they quickly distract a company from its original intention that advertising simply mirrors the attitudes and values of the surrounding culture. No doubt advertising, like the media of social communications in general, does act as a mirror. But, also like media in general, it is a mirror that helps shape the reality it reflects, and sometimes it presents a distorted image of reality.

Advertisers are selective about the values and attitudes to be fostered and encouraged, promoting some while ignoring others. This selectivity gives the lie to the notion that advertising does no more than reflect the surrounding culture. For example, the absence from advertising of certain racial and ethnic groups in some multi-racial or multi-ethnic societies can help to create problems of image and identity, especially among those neglected, and the almost inevitable impression in commercial advertising that an abundance of possessions leads to happiness and fulfillment can be both misleading and frustrating.

Advertising also has an indirect but powerful impact on society through its influence on media. Many publications and broadcasting operations depend on advertising revenue for survival. This often is true of religious media as well as commercial media. For their part, advertisers naturally seek to reach audiences; and the media, striving to deliver audiences to advertisers, must shape their content so to attract audiences of the size and

demographic purpose to provide profits to shareholders while supplying consumers with goods and services that add tangible benefits to their lives.

1.2.1. CSR as Public Relations

CSR sells. By appealing to customers' consciences and desires. CSR helps companies to build brand loyalty and develop a personal connection with their customers. Many corporate charity tie-ins gain companies access to target markets and the involvement of the charity gives the company's message much greater power. In our media saturated culture, companies are looking for ever more innovative ways to get across their message, and CSR offers up many potential avenues, such as word of mouth or guerilla marketing, for subtly reaching consumers. In fact, CSR create a language shift, a re-brand and a new caring image, but no substance.

CSR also helps to greenwash the company's image, to cover up negative impacts by saturating the media with positive images of the company's CSR credentials.

Since much of the business case for CSR depends on corporations being seen to be socially responsible, CSR will continue to be little more than PR for as long as it is easier and cheaper to spin than to change.

1.2.2. Corporate Citizenship: With responsibilities come rights

Corporations are not citizens, they are artificial legal persons. The term 'corporate citizen', used to describe corporations that are attempting to be socially responsible, creates a new image of the corporation as an entity which has rights, feelings, a legitimate voice in a democracy, and which behaves in a moral manner.

This kind of language shift creates a tangible shift in attitudes. Companies' involvement is bought by their 'commitment' to CSR and 'sustainability', and gives them the opportunity to dominate the agenda and put across their view of how the society should be run.

1.2.3 CSR as Public Private Partnerships

Many CSR activities can be defined as public-private partnerships (PPP). PPPs encompass a variety of arrangements where companies pool their resources with governmental, intergovernmental and / or civil society organisations. Examples relevant to CSR include running community development projects, sponsoring school playgrounds or providing healthcare. These projects blur the boundary between the role of governments and the role of companies. CSR is in itself a privatisation of a public function, since deciding what is appropriate behaviour for companies and regulating that should be the responsibility of a democracy and not of the companies themselves. CSR has shifted the ground towards privatisation. CSR makes government/corporate

relationships acceptable, generates contacts and builds trust and reputation to smooth the transition towards private ownership and control.

1.3. Ethics in Advertising

Ethics means a set of moral principles which govern a person's behavior or how the activity is conducted. And advertising means a mode of communication between a seller and a buyer. Thus ethics in advertising means a set of well-defined principles which govern the ways of communication taking place between the seller and the buyer. Ethics is the most important feature of the advertising industry. Though there are many benefits of advertising but then there are some points which don't match the ethical norms of advertising.

An ethical ad is the one which doesn't lie, doesn't make fake or false claims and is in the limit of decency. Nowadays, ads are more exaggerated and a lot of puffing is used. It seems like the advertisers lack knowledge of ethical norms and principles. They just don't understand and are unable to decide what is correct and what is wrong.

The main area of interest for advertisers is to increase their sales, gain more and more customers, and increase the demand for the product by presenting a well decorated, puffed and colorful ad. They claim that their product is the best, having unique qualities than the competitors, more cost effective, and more beneficial. But most of these ads are found to be false, misleading customers and unethical. The best example of these types of ads is the one which shows evening snacks for the kids, they use coloring and gluing to make the product look glossy and attractive to the consumers who are watching the ads on television and convince them to buy the product without giving a second thought.

Ethics in Advertising is directly related to the purpose of advertising and the nature of advertising. Sometimes exaggerating the ad becomes necessary to prove the benefit of the product. For e.g. a sanitary napkin ad which shows that when the napkin was dropped in a river by some girls, the napkin soaked whole water of the river. Thus, the purpose of advertising was only to inform women about the product quality. Obviously, every woman knows that this cannot practically happen but the ad was accepted. This doesn't show that the ad was unethical.

Ethics also depends on what we believe. If the advertisers make the ads on the belief that the customers will understand, persuade them to think, and then act on their ads, then this will lead to positive results and the ad may not be called unethical. But at the same time, if advertisers believe that they can fool their customers by showing any impractical things like just clicking fingers will make your home or office fully furnished or just

buying a lottery ticket will make you a millionaire, then this is not going to work out for them and will be called as unethical.

There are three consensus moral principles on the ethics of advertising:

Truthfulness, Social Responsibility and Upholding Human Dignity.

Generally, big companies never lie as they have to prove their points to various ad regulating bodies. Truth is always said but not completely. Sometimes it's better not to reveal the whole truth in the ad but at times truth has to be shown for betterment.

- Pharmaceutical Advertising - they help creating awareness, but one catchy point here is that the advertisers show what the medicine can cure but never talk about the side effects of that same thing or the risks involved in intake of it.
- Children - children are the major sellers of the ads and the product. They have the power to convince the buyers. But when advertisers are using children in their ad, they should remember not to show them alone doing their work on their own like brushing teeth, playing with toys, or infants holding their own milk bottles as everyone knows that no one will leave their kids unattended while doing all these activities. So showing parents also involved in all activities or things being advertised will be more logical.
- Alcohol - till today, there hasn't come any liquor ad which shows anyone drinking the original liquor. They use mineral water and sodas in their advertisements with their brand name. These types of ads are called surrogate ads. These type of ads are totally unethical when liquor ads are totally banned. Even if there are no advertisements for alcohol, people will continue drinking.
- Cigarettes and Tobacco - these products should be never advertised as consumption of these things is directly and badly responsible for cancer and other severe health issues. These are already banned in countries like India, Norway, Thailand, Finland and Singapore.
- Ads for social causes - these types of ads are ethical and are accepted by the people. But ads like condoms and contraceptive pills should be limited, as these are sometimes unethical, and are more likely to lose morality and decency at places where there is no educational knowledge about all these products.

Looking at all these above mentioned points, advertisers should start taking responsibility of self-regulating their ads by:

- ❖ Design self-regulatory codes in their companies including ethical norms, truth, decency, and legal points.
- ❖ Keep tracking the activities and remove ads which don't fulfill the codes.
- ❖ Inform the consumers about the self-regulatory codes of the company.
- ❖ Pay attention on the complaints coming from consumers about the product ads.
- ❖ Maintain transparency throughout the company and system.

When all the above points are implemented, they will result in:

- Making the company answerable for all its activities.
- Will reduce the chances of getting pointed out by the critics or any regulatory body.
- Will help gain confidence of the customers, make them trust the company and their products.

1.4. The effect of a firm's ethical and social responsibility on the advertising industry

Ethics and social responsibility means that businesses show concern for the people as well the environment in which they transact their businesses. It also means that the business organization communicates and enforces the values to everyone including the organizational practices as well as to the partners of the organization. As much as pursuing a social agenda does not translate into automatic increase in revenues or enhance public image at once: businesses that consistently pursue social responsibilities eventually earn a strong reputation with dividends in the form of consumer loyalty.

Today, advertisements from business entities that do not incorporate ethics and social responsibilities in their operations are not as effective with their advertisements as before. Research reveals that ethical practices and social responsibilities by businesses have become a vital component of marketing strategy by businesses. The acceptability of business behavior is determined by the customers, government regulators, competitors, interest groups, and the public as well as personal values and morals principles. Consumers as well as social advocate groups hold that businesses should not only focus on making profit but should also consider the implications of their activities on the society. Therefore, main aim of social responsibilities as an obligation on the part of a business should be to maximize its positive outcomes while minimizing the negative outcomes on the society.

There is a growing pressure for the advertisement campaigns to be socially, culturally and morally ethical.

As a result of consistent and seemingly unending string of ethical lapses across industries, businesses and in organizations, to greater extent has resulted in a crisis of trust in the market place. It is this numerous and highly publicized ethical breaches that have resulted into many firms and agents to be under constant public scrutiny (McKinney et al., 2010). In attempts to improve their image and their ethical performance, many of these firms have defined their ethical codes of conduct. The advertisement industry has come under constant frequent criticism for exaggerating and publishing misleading claims on products and services advertised. There is also an increasing perception on advertisements as being guilty of glorifying tendencies and habits regarded as undesirable and encouraging deviant culture in the society. However, as a result of increased consumer awareness concerning ethical and social responsibilities expected of the businesses entities, misleading or exaggerated advertisement claims tarnish the firm's credibility.

1.5. The role of ethical and social responsibility in achieving business objectives

Investing in the ethics and social responsibility practices is perceived as a long short-term investment with long-term benefits. The question then is whether firms will be willing to accept the short-term costs when their competitors in most cases are not. However, the vision of businesses in promoting ethical and social responsibility is to be accountable to a wide range of stakeholders, shareholders and investors. Key areas of focus, when it comes to Ethics and Social Responsibility, concerns environmental protection, employees' wellbeing, community as well as the civil society's welfare, both in the present and future.

Underpinning ethical and social responsibility practices for businesses is the idea that businesses can no longer act in isolation as economic entities detached from the broader society. Driving the issues of ethics and social responsibility is the shrinking role of the government, demand for more disclosure, increased customer interest and investor pressure, supplier relations and competitive labor markets. The benefits from adoption of ethical and social responsibility practices accrue not only to businesses but also to community and the general public as well as to the environment.

The benefits accruing to businesses from adoption of such ethical and social responsibility practices ultimately leads to the achievement of business objectives. By embracing ethical practices and engaging social responsibilities, the businesses will benefit from improved financial performance resulting from increased sales, reduced operating costs, enhanced reputation and brand image, greater ability to attract and retain employees as well as

increased productivity by the workers. These businesses will have increased access to capital; enjoy customer loyalty as well as product safety with a decreased liability. The overall net effect of these benefits is that the ultimate goal of profitability of the firm will be attained with a lot of ease as compared to firms that depend on advertisements alone as a means of marketing their products and services.

1.6. Effect of ethical and social responsibility practices on consumer behavior

Research reveals that increased ethical awareness by consumers in the modern times influences the way consumers behave towards products and services of different firms. Over the last few decades, ethics and social responsibility have increasingly become so fundamental in the modern business realm. Researchers attribute the development on the heightened media attention, pressure from interest groups, and the demand from stakeholders and consumers (Barnes, 1983). Ethics and social responsibility practices of firms have significant influence on consumer purchase behavior. That is, consumer purchasing decisions are influenced by socially responsible initiatives on the side of the firm. However, further insights into this topic points out that the effect of such initiatives will depend on the level of consumer awareness of the firm's involvement in the initiative. Building awareness, as argued by Varadarajan and Menon, is arguably the main purpose behind cause-related marketing. Numerous researches on impact of ethics and social responsibility on consumers' purchasing behavior have revealed that, a significant number of consumers are influenced by ethical firms that are socially responsible for their actions. It is undoubtedly clear that the impact of ethical and philanthropy business initiatives will influence consumer response towards the products or services of the said firm or business.

2. CONCLUSIONS

Advertisements do have a large impact on the audiences. It clarifies that advertisements really are one of the most powerful and strongest medium of mass communication and when authentic and unbiased messages are delivered through this medium, the products get an instant positive response in the market. It all depends on the advertisers, who introduce the products or services with complete authenticity and without forgetting their responsibility towards the community. The indispensable guarantors of ethically correct behavior by the advertising industry are the well-formed and responsible consciences of advertising professionals themselves: consciences sensitive to their duty not merely to serve the interests of those who commission and finance their work but also to

respect and uphold the rights and interests of their audiences and to serve the common good.

Advertisements do have a social responsibility and it wouldn't be wrong to state that people can be successfully made aware of the all the concerned and relevant social issues through this significant tool of mass communication. Advertisers should pay to attention that consumers in contemporary times are significantly influenced by ethical and social responsibility practices of businesses. It is evident also that businesses are increasingly investing in initiatives that endear them to the communities within which they operate. Therefore, in conclusion, ethical and social responsibilities should inform marketing strategies of businesses in the 21st century as a move to influence consumer behavior.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First of all, we are grateful to The Almighty God for establishing us to complete this study. We take this opportunity to record our sincere thanks to parents for their support and unceasing encouragement.

REFERENCES

1. Andrew C. Coors & Wayne Winegarden (2005). Corporate Social Responsibility—Or Good Advertising?, *Regulation Journal*, Briefly Noted, 11-12.
2. Arens W., Weigold M. F., Arens C. (2011). *Contemporary advertising and integrated marketing communications*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill Higher Education.
3. Battacharya C. B., Korschun D., Sen S. (2011). *Leveraging corporate responsibility: The stakeholder route to maximizing business and social value*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
4. Carroll A. B. (1979). A three-dimensional conceptual model of corporate social performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 4, 497-505.
5. Carroll A. B. (1991). The pyramid of corporate social responsibility: Toward the moral management of organizational stakeholders. *Business Horizons*, 34, 39-48.
6. Carroll A. B. (1999). Corporate social responsibility: Evolution of a definitional construct. *Business & Society*, 38, 268-295.
7. Dean D. (2004). Consumer reaction to negative publicity. *Journal of Business Communication*, 41, 192-211.
8. Debarati Dhar (2011). Advertising and its Social Responsibility, *Global Media Journal – Indian Edition/ Summer Issue*: 1-6.
9. Drumwright M. E., Murphy P. E. (2004). How advertising practitioners view ethics: Moral muteness, moral myopia, and moral imagination. *Journal of Advertising*, 33, 7-24.
10. Drumwright M. E., Murphy P. E. (2009). The current state of advertising ethics: Industry and academic perspectives. *Journal of Advertising*, 38, 83-107.

11. Friedman M. (1970, September 13). The social responsibility of business is to increase its profits. *New York Times Magazine*, p. 33.
12. Hall, D. & Jones, S. C. (2008). Corporate social responsibility, condition branding and ethics in marketing. In D. Spanjaard, S. Denize & N. Sharma (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Australian and New Zealand Marketing Academy Conference* (pp. 81-88). Sydney, Australia: Australian and New Zealand Marketing Academy.
13. Haski-Leventhal D. (2012). Corporate responsibility and responsible management education in the eyes of MBA Students.
14. Hildebrand D., Sen S., Battacharya C. B. (2011). Corporate social responsibility: A corporate marketing perspective. *European Journal of Marketing*, 45, 1353-1364.
15. Hyman M. M. (2009). Responsible ads: A workable ideal. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 87, 199-210.
16. John P. Foley & Pierfranco Pastore (1997). Pontifical Council for Social Communications, *Ethics in Advertising*, Vatican City, Feast of the Chair of St. Peter the Apostle.
17. Keith N. K., Pettijohn C. E., Burnett M. S. (2008). Ethics in advertising: Differences in industry values and student perceptions. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 12, 81-96.
18. Norris V. P. (1983). Toward a social control in the advertising agency. *Journal of Advertising*, 12, 30-33.
19. Paek H. J., Hove T. (2010). Advertising as social responsibility institution. In *Proceedings of 2010 Annual American Academy of Advertising Conference*, 27-28.
20. Powell S. (2011). The nexus between ethical corporate marketing, ethical corporate identity and corporate social responsibility: An internal organisational perspective. *European Journal of Marketing*, 45, 1365-1379.
21. Preston I. (2010). Interaction of law and ethics in matters of advertisers' responsibility for protecting consumers. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 44, 259-264.
22. Waller D. S., Lanis R. (2009). Corporate social responsibility (CSR) disclosure of advertising agencies: An exploratory analysis of six holding companies' annual reports. *Journal of Advertising*, 38, 109-121.